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● A new species of the genus *Pedopodisma* Zheng, 1980 (Orthoptera: Acrididae: Melanoplinae) from Jiangxi, China

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Abstract: A new species of locust, *Pedopodisma meilingensis* sp. nov., representing a new provincial record for the genus, is described and illustrated from Jiangxi, China. The new species is similar to *P. dolichypyga* Huang, 1988, but differs in: **1)** Head with distinct median carina; **2)** Cerci with bases wider and slightly upturned at apices; **3)** Body larger, ♂ 24.02 mm, ♀ 29.00–30.00 mm; **4)** Tegmina longer, ♂ 1.59 mm, ♀ 1.90–1.95 mm.

Keywords: Distribution, morphology, new provincial record, Oriental Region, Podismini, taxonomy

● 中国江西省小蹦蝗属一新种（直翅目：蝗科：黑蝗亚科）

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摘要: 本文描绘了一种产于中国江西的蝗虫新种——梅岭小蹦蝗 *Pedopodisma meilingensis* sp. nov., 并且其代表了该属在江西的省级新纪录。该新种近似于长尾小蹦蝗 *P. dolichypyga* Huang, 1988, 但区别于 **1)** 头部背面具明显中隆线; **2)** 尾须基部更阔且末端上翻; **3)** 体型更大, ♂ 24.02 mm, ♀ 29.00–30.00 mm; **4)** 前翅更长, ♂ 1.59 mm, ♀ 1.90–1.95 mm。

关键词: 分布, 形态, 省级新纪录, 东洋区, 秃蝗族, 分类学

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Introduction

Pedopodisma emeiensis (Yin, 1980) was described by Yin (1980) and originally attributed to the genus *Micropodisma* Dvornar-Zapolskij, 1932 as *M. emeiensis* Yin, 1980. This species placed in *Micropodisma* seems inappropriate, because it has extremely small tegmina while *Micropodisma* is completely wingless. Later in the same year, Zheng (1980) established the genus *Pedopodisma* Zheng, 1980, with *P. microptera* Zheng, 1980 as the type species by original designation. The type localities of the two species are identical. Yin *et al.* (1996) transferred *M. emeiensis* to *Pedopodisma* and simultaneously synonymized *P. microptera* with *P. emeiensis*.

The species of *Pedopodisma* are mainly distributed in mountainous environments with an altitude of over 500 meters in the northwest, southwest and central regions of China. Before this study, fifteen known species have been recorded (Yin 1980; Zheng 1980; Huang 1988; Wang 1992; Zhang 1994; Zheng & Chen 1995; Yin *et al.* 1996, 2012; Wang & Li 1996; Fu & Zheng 1996; He *et al.* 1999; Zheng & Huo 2000; Zheng & Li 2000; Zhong & Zheng 2004; Zheng & Ren 2005; Zheng & Shi 2006). In this study, the main differences between the genera *Pedopodisma* and *Sinopodisma* Chang, 1940 are present, and a new species of *Pedopodisma* from Jiangxi Province of China is described.

Material and methods

Specimens were collected by Yan-Long Li and Jing-Zhe Du at Meiling, Jiangxi, China, with altitude from 500 to 800 m. Images were taken with a XF 30 mm macro lens on a Fujifilm XH2 camera.

The material examined for this study is deposited in the following institutional collections: **MYNU**—Invertebrate collection of Mianyang Normal University, Mianyang, China; **MHBU**—Museum of Hebei University, Baoding, China.

Measurements were made with MATO software (Liu *et al.* 2023) from pictures in the following ways: **body length**—dorsally from the fastigium vertex to the distal end of abdomen; **pronotum length**—dorsally along the median carina; **hind femur length**—laterally, maximum possible measurement of the hind femur.

Taxonomy

Family Acrididae MacLeay, 1821 蝗科

Subfamily Melanoplinae Scudder, 1897 黑蝗亚科

Tribe Podismini Jacobson, 1905 秃蝗族

Subtribe Tonkinacridina Ito, 2015 越北蝗亚族

Genus *Pedopodisma* Zheng, 1980 小蹦蝗属

Zheng 1980: 336, 347 (description; key to species; 3 spp.); Zheng 1985: 160 (characteristics; key to species; 3 spp.); Zheng 1993: (characteristics; key to species; 5 spp.); Yin *et al.* 1996: 531 (catalogue; 3 spp.); Zheng & Huo 2000: (characteristics; key to species; 10 spp.); Zheng & Ren 2005: 93 (key to species; 12 spp.); Lian Z-M 2006: (characteristics; key to species; 10 spp.; distribution).

Type species: *Pedopodisma emeiensis* (Yin, 1980) (= *Micropodisma emeiensis* Yin, 1980 = *Pedopodisma microptera* Zheng, 1980) (Fig. 1), by original designation.

Description: Male. Body size small. Fastigium sloping forward, significantly enlarged in front of eyes. Width in front of eyes obviously larger than width of frontal ridge between antennae. Face sloping backwards in lateral view. Frontal ridge with lateral margins subparallel, with shallow longitudinal sulcus. Eyes oval, with longitudinal diameter 1.20–1.58 times as long as horizontal diameter and 1.20–1.58 times as long as subocular furrow. Antennae filiform, slender, retrad reaching bases of hind femora. Pronotum in both genders with anterior margins nearly straight, posterior margins nearly straight and concave at middle; median carina indistinct and lateral carinae absent;

FIGURE 1. *Pedopodisma emeiensis* (Yin, 1980) (© Hao Ju).

prozona 1.85–2.30 times as long as metazona. Prosternal spine conical. Tegmina extremely small, with apices slightly or not surpassing posterior margin of abdominal tergite I; hind wings absent. Hind femora with upper carinae smooth; apices of lower knee lobes rounded. Hind tibiae without external apical spines. Arolium between claws large, exceeding apices of claws. Tympanal organ opening developed, oval. Male abdominal tergite X widely divided in middle, without or with indistinct furculae. Epiproct nearly triangular. Epiphallus nearly bridge-shaped, with ancorae and paired lophi of short-rod or irregular shapes.

Female. Body size medium. Epiproct subtriangular, with one blunt circular at apex. Cerci short conical, apices sharp. Lower ovipositor with posterior edge protrudes in triangle.

Differential diagnosis. *Pedopodisma* (Figs 1; 2A, B) is similar in appearance to *Sinopodisma* Chang, 1940 (Figs 2C, D), and their main differences are shown in the Table 1.

TABLE 1. Main differences between *Pedopodisma* Zheng, 1980 (Fig. 3A) and *Sinopodisma* Chang, 1940 (Fig. 3B).

Characters	<i>Pedopodisma</i> Zheng, 1980	<i>Sinopodisma</i> Chang, 1940
Tegmina length	♂ 0.2 mm–1.59 mm; ♀ 0.4 mm–1.95 mm	♂ 2.5 mm–4.5 mm; ♀ 3.3 mm–6.5 mm
Tegmina shape	extremely small, slightly visible, thin and transparent, far from reaching tympanic membrane apparatus	larger, scale-like, lateral, reaching or covering tympanic membrane apparatus

FIGURE 2. Live species of *Pedopodisma* and *Sinopodisma*: **A, B** *Pedopodisma wanxianensis* Zheng & Chen, 1995, Hubei, China (© Qian-Le Lu) **C** *Sinopodisma zhengi* Liang & Lin, 1994, Yunnan, China (© Qing-Bo Huo) **D** *Sinopodisma lofaoshana* (Tinkham, 1936), Guangxi, China (© Qing-Bo Huo).

***Pedopodisma meilingensis* sp. nov.** 梅岭小蹦蝗

<https://zoobank.org/26144F8C-EDD5-4314-A29E-E0BC30BE53EE>

Figs 4A–G; 5A–F; 6A, D

Type material. **Holotype:** ♂ (MHB), **CHINA, Jiangxi:** Meiling [梅岭], 17.X.2020, Yan-Long Li leg. **Paratypes:** 2♀ (MYNU), same as holotype; 2♂♂1♀ (MHB), same as holotype except 768 m, 28.IX.2024, Jing-Zhe Du leg.

Etymology. The specific epithet is named for the type locality, Meiling.

Measurement (in mm). Body length: ♂ 24.20, ♀ 29.00–30.00; pronotum length: ♂ 4.95, ♀ 5.02–5.05; hind femur length: ♂ 12.84, ♀ 14.8–15.3.

Description. Coloration. Body yellowish-brown. Eyes brown and wide black bands present behind. Antennae yellowish-brown, with slightly dark apices. Black brown stripe present on either side of head dorsum and median carina of pronotum (not obvious in female). Tegmina brown. Abdomen with wide black longitudinal bands until 10th abdominal segment X in male and VI in female in lateral views. Hind femora yellowish-green, each with 8–10 dark small spots at upper side, sometimes inconspicuous; knee lobe black. Hind tibiae blue-green; spines black.

Male (Figs 4A, C–F). Body size small, with head shorter than anterior pronotum and back plate. Top of the head tilt and protrude in obtuse angle downwards. Entire length of facial protrusion has a longitudinal groove, slightly enlarged at middle monocular region. Eyes oval, 1.2 times as long as wide, and 1.6 times than sulcus. Antennae filiform, reaching bases of hind legs, middle segments 2.8 times as long as wide. Pronotum slightly rough,

FIGURE 3. Comparison of tegmina between *Podopodisma* and *Sinopodisma*: **A** *Podopodisma wanxianensis* Zheng & Chen, 1995, male **B** *Sinopodisma lofaoshana* (Tinkham, 1936), male. Scale = 1 cm.

nearly straight in anterior margin and slightly depression in median posterior margin. Median carina totally distinct, slightly cut by last transverse sulci; prozona 2.0 times of metazona in length; lateral carinae absent. Prosternal process conical, slightly backwards, sharp at apex. Metosternal lobes with width equal to length, metasternal lobes slightly separate. Tegmina extremely small, scaly, not reached posterior margin of abdominal tergite I, sharp at apices. Tympanal organ distinct, nearly circular. Upper carina of hind femur with slightly teeth; upper basal lobe of hind femur on outer side distinctly longer than lower one. Hind tibia with 11 spines at inner side and 9 spines at outer side, external apical spine absent. Arolium between claws large, widely rounded, exceeding apices of claws. Epiproct triangle, with longitudinal groove in median. Cerci longer, straight in apex, nearly reaching apices of epiproct. Epiphallus inverted trapezoid; bridge with anterior margin straight, posterior margin retrad concaved, wide; ancorae angular, curving inwards, with non-sharp tips; anterior projections angular, with median carina and higher than ancorae in dorsal and ventral views; lateral plates incline outwards, and posterior projections extending outwards; lophi large. In phallic complex, length of the apical valves of penis equal to that of cingulum valves; apodemes nearly equal than basal valves of penis, and slightly sharp at apices; basal valves of penis large in lateral view.

Female (Figs 4B, G). Antennae filiform, reaching or slightly exceeding posterior margin of pronotum, middle segments 1.8 times as long as wide. Epiproct subtriangular, with one blunt circular at apex. Cerci short conical, apices sharp. Posterior margin of lower ovipositor protrudes in triangular shape.

Differential diagnosis. *P. meilingensis* **sp. nov.** is most similar to *P. dolichypyga* Huang, 1988. The diagnostic differences of the two species are listed in Table 2.

Biological notes. This new species overwinters as eggs, and adults can be seen every August. From September to October, both males and females complete mating. It likes to inhabit in forest environments above 500 meters of altitude. Mating pictures can be referenced in Fig. 6D.

This new species overwinters as eggs, and adults can be seen every August. From September to October, both males and females complete mating. It likes to inhabit in forest environments above 500 meters of altitude. The main hosts and habitat, as well as image of male and female mating, are shown in Figs 6A–D.

Distribution. China (Jiangxi) (Fig. 7).

FIGURE 4. *Pedopodisma meilingensis* sp. nov.: A, C–F holotype, male A habitus, lateral view C sternal plate, ventral view D tegmina, lateral view E abdominal terminal, dorsal view F cerci, lateral view B, G paratype, female B habitus, dorsal view G habitus, lateral view. Scales = 1 cm for A, B, G and 1 mm for C–F.

TABLE 2. Diagnostic differences between *Pedopodisma meilingensis* sp. nov. and *P. dolichypyga* Huang, 1988.

Characters	<i>P. meilingensis</i> sp. nov.	<i>P. dolichypyga</i> Huang, 1988
Head	median carina present	median carina absent
Cerci Shape	bases wider and slightly upturned at apices	bases wider and slightly curved downwards at apices
Body length	♂ 24.02 mm, ♀ 29.00–30.00 mm	♂ 16.50–19.20 mm, ♀ 21.60–23.01 mm
Tegmina length	♂ 1.59 mm, ♀ 1.90–1.95 mm	♂ 0.80 mm–1.00 mm, ♀ 1.00–1.50 mm

FIGURE 5. *Pedopodisma meilingensis* sp. nov., holotype, male: A–C dorsal, lateral, and ventral views of epiphallus D–F dorsal, lateral, and ventral views of phallic complex. Scales = 0.5 mm.

FIGURE 6. *Pedopodisma meilingensis* sp. nov.: A a live male on host plant B, C habitat environment (Jiangxi, China) D a pair of mating male and female. (© Yan-Long Li).

FIGURE 7. Distribution map of *Pedopodisma* species.

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